

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D5.2.1

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	18/07/2024		Silvia Fraterrigo Garofalo Debora Fino

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Main objectives achieved

The main objectives of this RM are the definition and selection of the technological solutions available to be tested at the industrial level for CO₂ capture and conversion and the expected results from the activities foreseen in this RM will lead, through a comparison between the different technologies at the level of applied research, to the definition of the best technologies available in this sector.

Task 5.2.1 has been completed (more details from page 9 to page 13) and in particular the main results achieved are:

- Development and optimization of materials and systems for CO₂ capture.
- Synthesis, characterization and tests on adsorption materials
- Characterization and test on quarry waste material from RM1

B) Research Module n° 5

CO₂ capture and conversion platform: biochemical, chemo-catalytic and electrochemical conversion processes

RM5 will deal with Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. CO₂ is one of the main responsible of the rapid rise in global temperature. The RM5 plans to identify a suitable technology for the capture and conversion of CO₂ for industrial application in a steady state. Mineral capture of CO₂ from industrial/engines emissions will be applied and evaluated in synergy with the other carbon capture methods with a view to providing a diverse portfolio of solutions to the carbon dioxide rise in the atmosphere. Carbon capture and storage will complete the previous approaches to the reduction of the impact of urban and industrial waste by acting on the gaseous waste from anthropic activities. The RM5 also aims to develop a suitable technology for the subsequent conversion of trapped CO₂ for the synthesis of methanol and other high-value molecules through multiple synthetic bio-chemical, chemical and electrochemical strategies. The processes will be optimized first on a laboratory scale and subsequently validated on a pilot scale.

List of Deliverables

Table - List of Deliverables

N°	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE *	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
5.1	Data acquisition and material characterization	R	Collection of data, Characterization of the composition of gases at the emittee for the identification of the specifications required for CO ₂ capture and conversion, selection of the experimental set-ups.	POLITO	PU	10
5.2.1	Development and optimization of materials and systems for CO ₂ capture.	R	Synthesis, characterization and tests on adsorption materials	POLITO-UNITO	PU	20
5.2.2	CO ₂ Conversion by thermochemistry.	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.3	CO ₂ Conversion by electrochemistry	R	Tests, evaluation of material conversion capacity and product characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.2.4	Biochemical conversion of CO ₂	R	Optimization of the growth process and products characterization	POLITO	PU	30
5.3	Products application	R	Investigation of market trends and application of products	POLITO	PU	32
5.4	Environmental	R	Comparison between	POLITO	PU	32

	constraints		the three processes of CO ₂ being equal from an environmental sustainability point of view			
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List of Milestones

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M5.1	CO ₂ capture and conversion materials	5	10	At least one material to be tested for each conversion process and also microorganism for the biochemical process will be selected.
M5.2	CO ₂ capture and conversion processes	5	32	The best process will be identified among those investigated from a technical, economic and environmental point of view.

C) General description of the Deliverable D5.2.1

Development and optimization of materials and systems for CO₂ capture.

During this task Polito and Unito will synthesize the materials selected in the previous task. Unito will deal with the characterization of these materials. Polito will test the materials on the flows identified in the previous task to select the best performance. Morphological characterization, chemical analysis and surface properties of materials will be performed to select the best solution in terms of selectivity, working capacity, resistance to poisoning and renewability of the active phases. Part of the tasks will be dedicated to the use of materials deriving from RM1 appropriately functionalized and to the comparison of their properties with other materials of interest. The best solution can be tested on a larger scale.

D) Deliverable D5.2.1

CO₂ capture:

Due to the huge volume of anthropogenic carbon dioxide (CO₂) production, CO₂ is deemed the largest greenhouse gas contributor to global warming. Since the Industrial Revolution era, the atmospheric concentration of this gas has grown exceeding the value of 400 ppm registered in recent years^{1,2}. To overcome this challenge many technologies have been developed in the area of post-combustion carbon dioxide capture in the last decades. Magnesium-based materials are considered in the literature as good candidates for CO₂ adsorption and release applications. Indeed, these sorbents possess appropriate surface basicity that allows their use in the intermediate temperature range (200 - 400 °C). Furthermore, through focused heat treatments, proper regeneration of the sorbent with available cyclic uses is possible^{3–5}. From a chemical and environmental safety perspective, magnesium-based materials can be considered 'green materials' as they are non-toxic, non-corrosive and environmentally friendly. Reflecting on a real-life application, typically, the composition of flue gases released by natural gas-fired power plants is 8–10% CO₂, 18–20% H₂O, 2–3% O₂, and 67–72% N₂. The presence of water is a source of a wealth of effects on CO₂ adsorption⁶. Indeed, an adsorption competition between water and CO₂ may occur when working with physical adsorbent (e.g., zeolites⁷, activated carbons⁸, MOFs⁹), since, according to individual cases, water can strongly compete with CO₂ reducing drastically the uptakes. Conversely, magnesium-based sorbents can react with CO₂ in a wide range of temperatures, proving noteworthy uptakes even in the presence of humidity, which can promote adsorption⁵.

We focused on Layered double hydroxides (LDHs) which are inorganic crystalline materials composed of divalent and trivalent metal ions characterised by interesting features namely fast adsorption rate, ease of regeneration, and good thermal stability. Conventionally, LDHs are made of magnesium and aluminium ions with different atomic ratios¹⁰. Through heat treatment of

LDHs, a mixed oxide structure (LDO) denoted by a high surface area (an important feature for a good sorbent) is obtained. Moreover, their crystalline structure makes it possible to have a material with high defectiveness and dispersion of the main basic sites, namely Mg sites. The impregnation of alkali metal salts would encourage the CO₂ adsorption performance of LDOs by increasing surface defects. The uptakes rise in the presence of water vapour compared to dry conditions, since under a humid gas the adsorption proceeds via the formation of transient hydroxylate species which then react with CO₂ to form carbonates.

We prepared LDO sorbents from the starting material LDH (3:1) undoped and one doped with 20 wt.% of K₂CO₃ (wet impregnation, labelled K-LDO)11. First CO₂ adsorption and desorption experiments were conducted in a laboratory experimental reactor set-up. The sorbent first underwent thermal pre-treatment in hydrogen (5 vol-% H₂ in N₂) to clean the surface and then the adsorption test was conducted with a flow of 5 vol-% CO₂ in N₂ at 250 °C (total flow rate of 90 mL/min, atmospheric pressure). Wet adsorption tests were carried out with a humid feed of 5 vol-% CO₂ in N₂ (RH of 10%) at 250 °C. CO₂-TPD experiments were performed to observe the balance of carbon atoms and the surface basic strength. After dry adsorption, the LDO sorbent exhibits good adsorptive properties at 250 °C. indeed, potassium carbonate increased the amount of CO₂ adsorbed (+ 55 %), which was also confirmed by desorption tests (up to 500 °C). The CO₂ uptake reached 0.57 mmol g⁻¹ of adsorbed gas in wet conditions. Desorption experiments confirmed the adsorption outcomes, revealing that potassium benefits the adsorption process, increasing the number and typologies of carbonate species on the material surface (300 – 400 °C). The presence of water in the feed gas further improved the strength of carbonate species on the material surface, as evidenced by desorption peaks at high temperatures (> 400 °C). These results are summarised in Fig.1.

As part of collaborations between project partners, we received silicate and marble-based samples (mining waste) from the Department of Earth Sciences of the University of Turin. TGA analyses were conducted as preliminary screening for possible application as sorbents. Thermal analysis was conducted in the temperature range of 40 - 900 °C. The gneiss sample loses 1.15 % of its weight. Since it is a silicate-based material, this weight loss could be related to the desorption of H₂O and some weakly interacting carbonate species CO₃²⁻. The marble sample loses 42 % of its weight. Since it is a MCO₃-based material, this weight loss at high temperatures could be related to the desorption of the CO₂ fraction throughout the sample (which is 44%) (Fig.2 A). Morphological analysis (FESEM) did not reveal any significant differences. At low magnifications, the Marmo sample appears relatively smooth (Fig. 2 B). Upon closer examination, nanometric globular structures with smooth sides are observed. The Gneiss sample exhibits a more jagged surface with flakes measuring a few hundred nanometers. This analysis corroborated the results of N₂ physisorption at -196 °C since both materials are characterised by a low surface area (gneiss 5.3 m² g⁻¹ and marble 1.5 m² g⁻¹). According to the TGA outcomes, the activation temperatures (before adsorption tests) were set at 400 °C and 550 °C for gneiss and marble samples, respectively. The sorbents first underwent thermal pre-treatment in nitrogen to clean the surface

and then the adsorption test was conducted with a flow of 5 vol-% CO₂ in N₂ at 25 and 250 °C (total flow rate of 90 mL/min, atmospheric pressure). Adsorption data revealed that physisorption was the predominant mechanism at play since no appreciable results were obtained. Gneiss showed adsorptive capacity only at 25 °C with 18.5 μmol g⁻¹. Conversely, the marble sample adsorbed 37.1 and 4.9 μmol g⁻¹ at 25 and 250 °C respectively (Fig. 3). One of the crucial factors influencing adsorption is the surface area of the material. In our study, both marble and gneiss exhibited very low surface areas. This is a significant finding, as a low surface area directly limits the number of adsorption sites available, thus impacting the overall adsorption capacity of the material. In light of the results obtained with the marble and gneiss samples, it can be stated that these materials are not currently suitable for use as adsorbent materials. However, they could be subjected to appropriate treatments to modify their chemical and physical characteristics, thereby enhancing their suitability for this application.

To summarise, LDO-based materials possess suitable characteristics for the proposed application; whereas, marble and gneiss samples should undergo further engineering treatments, as mentioned above. All the materials in this report were tested in a laboratory set-up. We have been unable to test these materials on a larger scale at this time, as no company has contributed to the project; consequently, we do not have the appropriate facilities for scaling up the process.

Fig. 1: A) Layered Double Oxides uptake curves and B) CO₂-TPD profiles.

A)

B)

Fig. 2: A) TGA analyses plot and B) FESEM images.

Fig. 3: CO₂ uptakes of marble and gneiss samples.

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